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Urban Air Mobility: Evaluating Exposure to Lightning Strikes

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Motivation & Outline

- Urban Air Mobility (UAM)
- eVTOL stands for electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing
- The growing interest in UAM and the rapid development of eVTOL technology necessitate research into operational safety, particularly in extreme weather conditions like lightning strikes.

Image Source: Eve Air Mobility. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.eveairmobility.com/>

Technological Advances and Challenges

- eVTOLs: Cutting Travel Time and Emissions
- A Sustainable Alternative to Urban Mobility
- Faster Commutes, Lower CO₂
- Quiet, Efficient, and Green Urban Travel
- Addressing Infrastructure and Weather Challenges

Image Source: Eve Air Mobility. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.eveairmobility.com/>

UAM – eVTOL Concept of Operations

- eVTOLs will operate within designated UAM corridors.
- Vertiports will serve as key nodes, enabling point-to-point connections within the UAM network.
- Advanced systems will monitor obstacles and adapt eVTOL flight paths to varying traffic levels, ensuring safe and responsive flight paths within evolving UAM corridors.

Image Source: FAA. Urban Air Mobility – Concepts of Operation v2.0

Lightning and UAM: The Problem

- Urban areas are more prone to lightning due to increased convective activity and pollution.
- eVTOLs' low-altitude flights and reliance on electrical systems make them vulnerable to lightning.
- How can we ensure the safety of eVTOLs in such a challenging atmospheric environment?

Images Source: Kim et al, Effects of lightning on UAM aircraft.

Urban Environment

Storm Severity

Polluted vs. Pristine: Pollution increases storm intensity and cloud formation dynamics.

Image Source: Naccarato et al, Evidence of thermal and aerosol effects on the cloud-to-ground lightning density and polarity over large urban areas of Southeastern Brazil.

Image Source: Rosenfeld et al., Flood or Drought: How Do Aerosols Affect Precipitation?

Urban Effect

Maps Correlation: (a) Lightning density, (b) São Paulo's urbanization, and (c) heat islands.

Lightning on eVTOL

CHARACTERISTICS OF UAM AIRCRAFT AND ASSOCIATED LIGHTNING EFFECTS

Characteristics	Problems	Lightning Effects
composite materials	low electrical conductivity	high structural damage
low velocity	lightning dwell time	
low altitude urban flight	exposure to urban environment	exposure to cloud-to-ground discharge
small size	low magnetic permeability	low electromagnetic shielding effect
large windshield		
electric engine	high electromagnetic sensitivity	high electromagnetic interference effect
avionics		

Table Source: Kim et al, Effects of lightning on UAM aircraft.

Lightning protection measurements:

- Component placement
- Shielding and grounding
- Placing components in less vulnerable zones

Challenges:

- Robust protection adds weight
- Weight is critical for battery efficiency

Some possibilities:

- Adjust of flight paths and schedules to avoid high lightning activity using real-time lightning monitoring and warning system data.
- Set of guidelines for safety operations in various weather conditions.
- eVOTL's protection must be adjusted to urban environment, take into consideration the weight constraints.

The discussions continue with an ongoing study and the results will be available in the future.

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Thank you!

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